

Study in some Heterochelates: Part VI

Cu(II), Ni(II)+NTA or Histidine+Oxyacids and Mercapto Acids

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Formation constants, $K_{\text{Ni.Hist}}$ where L = hydroxy or mercapto acid, $K_{\text{Ni.NTA}}$ where L = mercapto acid and $K_{\text{Cu.NTA}}$ where L = hydroxy acid, have been determined by using the modified method of Irving-Rossotti titration technique. Both hydroxy and thioacids behave alike as secondary ligands. It has been inferred that the contribution of π interaction in stabilizing M-S bond in complex is not very significant.

STUDY of the mixed ligand systems MAL, where M = Cu²⁺ or Ni²⁺; A = nitrilotriacetate anion (NTA) and L = different amino acids¹⁻³ or polyhydroxy aromatic compounds⁴ has been reported earlier. The ternary systems Zn.NTA.L, where L = mercapto acids have also been studied⁵. In the present investigation attempt has been made to study the systems MAL, where M = Cu²⁺ or Ni²⁺; A = histidine (Hist.), NTA or ethylenediaminetetraacetate ion (EDTA); L = hydroxy or mercapto acids. These systems are interesting because they throw some light on the relative stabilities of the M-O and M-S bonds.

Histidine⁶ and NTA¹ are known to form 1:1 complexes with Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ at low pH and the compounds are stable at higher pH, where the combination of the secondary ligands starts. The reaction can be shown as follows:

$$K_{MAL} = \frac{[MAL]}{[MA][L]}$$

The mixed ligand formation constants K_{MAL} have been determined by using an extension of Irving-Rossotti titration technique as used in earlier communications⁷.

Experimental and Calculations

Glycollic acid (Riedel, pure) lactic acid (May and Baker), malic acid (Riedel, pure), thioglycollic acid (E.Merck, pure), thiolactic acid (Fluka, pure), thiomalic acid (TMA) (Fluka, pure), were used as secondary ligands. Histidine (E.Merck, pure) and NTA (Cornbrook-Bucks, England, pure) were used as primary ligands. Ni(II) and Cu(II) perchlorates were

prepared from the corresponding carbonates and the metal contents were determined and checked. Other reagents used were perchloric acid (Baker, analysed), sodium perchlorate (Fluka, pure), sodium hydroxide (Chemapol, G.R.). All solutions have been prepared in conductivity water.

Metrohm E350 A pH meter (accuracy ± 0.05) was used and the titrations were carried out at 30°, using constant temperature bath (accuracy $\pm 0.1^\circ$).

Following solutions were prepared, volume was raised to 50 ml. in each case. The ionic strength of each solution was initially made 0.2M.

- 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M histidine + 0.178M sodium perchlorate.
- 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M histidine + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.176M sodium perchlorate.
- 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M secondary ligand + 0.002M perchloric acid + 0.176M sodium perchlorate.
- 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M histidine + 0.002M secondary ligands (L) + 0.174M sodium perchlorate.

For NTA systems:

- 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M NTA + 0.178M sodium perchlorate.
- 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M NTA + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.176M sodium perchlorate.
- 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.006M perchloric acid + 0.002M secondary ligand (L) + 0.172M sodium perchlorate.
- 0.02M perchloric acid + 0.002M NTA + 0.002M secondary ligand (L) + 0.002M metal perchlorate + 0.174M sodium perchlorate.

The above solutions were titrated against standard (·2*M*) alkali. *pH* was plotted against the volume of the alkali. The representative plots in case of Ni.NTA, thioglycollic acid and Ni.histidine.glycollic acid have been presented in the Figs. 1 and 2.

because Cu(II) gets reduced to Cu(I). In case of Ni.NTA.TMA, Ni.histidine.TMA and Ni.NTA.hydroxy acids systems separation between 3 and 4 curves was very small at high *pH* and hence calculation could not be done. The separation at high *pH* however,

Fig. 1. Ni.NTA.Thioglycollic acid
 1. NTA
 2. M+NTA
 3. Thioglycollic acid
 4. M+NTA+Thioglycollic acid

The curves in case of other Cu(II) and Ni(II) complex systems were of same type. The nature of the curves can be interpreted as done in earlier publications⁵. As is evident from curves 1 and 2, Ni.NTA and Ni.histidine 1 : 1 complexes are formed at low *pH* and are stable at high *pH*, because the horizontal distance remains constant upto *pH* ~ 8.5 in case of NTA and upto *pH* ~ 7.5 in case of histidine. Below, this, the curves start converging indicating absence of hydrolysis or hydroxo complex formation. In the curve 3, one or three equivalent extra acid have been added in case of histidine and NTA, respectively, in order to account for the extra hydrogen ions liberated due to the combination of the primary ligands histidine or NTA, with the metal ion in case of curve 4. From the horizontal distance between curve 3 and 4, $\bar{n}$ and *pL* can be calculated using same equation as in earlier cases⁷. Precise values of K_{MAL}^{Ni} were obtained by using the method of averages⁸. The values thus obtained have been presented in Table 1 and 2. Such titrations were not possible in case of Cu.histidine hydroxy acids, because the hydroxy acids combine before Cu.histidine 1 : 1 formation is complete. In case of Cu(II), work could not be carried out with mercapto acids also

indicates low values for the complex formation constants.

TABLE 1. MIXED LIGAND FORMATION OF SOME HETEROCHELATES OF BIVALENT NI AND CU AT 30°

L	log $K_{Ni.Hist.L}^{Ni.Hist.}$	log $K_{Cu.Hist.L}^{Cu.Hist.}$	Δ
Thioglycollic acid	5.86 ± (0.06)	—	0.79
Thiolic acid	6.46 ± (0.01)	—	0.77
Thiomalic acid	—	—	—
Glycollic acid	3.53 ± (0.01)	—	1.18
Lactic acid	4.07 ± (0.04)	—	0.88
Malic acid	4.57 ± (0.04)	—	0.85

In case of hydroxy acids, separation between curve 3 and 4 was attained at high *pH* 9 to 10, in both the cases where Histidine (in Ni complexes) or NTA (in Cu complexes) were the primary ligands. However, no hydrolysis is indicated and hence calculations have been carried out, considering the formation of only mixed ligand complex MAL. In case of hydroxy acid it has been considered that hydrogen of the OH is liberated as a result of complexation. This has been amply supported by various workers⁹⁻¹².

The values of the formation constants in case of the binary systems Cu(II) hydroxy acid have also been calculated by using Irving-Rossotti titration technique for comparison. The values in case of binary systems of Ni have been taken from our previous publications^{13,14}.

TABLE 2. MIXED LIGAND FORMATION OF SOME HETERO-CHELATES OF BIVALENT NI AND CU AT 30°

L	log $K_{Ni.NTA.Ni.NTA.L}^{Ni.NTA}$	log $K_{Cu.NTA.Cu.NTA.L}^{Cu.NTA}$	Δ
Thioglycollic acid	4.76 ± (0.05)	—	1.88
Thiolactic acid	4.54 ± (0.06)	—	2.63
Thiomalic acid	—	—	—
Glycollic acid	—	4.64	1.55
Lactic acid	—	5.36	1.20
Malic acid	—	5.53	2.90

$$\Delta = K_{MAL}^{MA} - K_{ML}^M$$

Fig. 2. Ni-Histidine Glycollic acid.

1. Histidine
2. M + histidine
3. Glycollic acid
4. M + histidine + Glycollic acid

Discussion

It is observed that in all the cases K_{MAL} have a lower value than K_{ML} . This can be explained to be due to the electrostatic repulsion between the incoming charged hydroxy and mercapto acid ions and already existing charged ion histidine or NTA. The value of K_{MAL} is higher, where A = histidine. This is because histidine has two negative charges

and hence exerts lesser repulsion on the incoming ligand than NTA with three negative charges. Thiomalate ion with bigger size and three negative charges faces too much of repulsion and steric hindrance from binary ligands and hence the values of $K_{NTA.TMA}$ and $K_{Histidine.TMA}$ are very low and the systems could not be studied.

It is observed that in [Ni.Histidine.L] systems, the behaviour of mercapto and hydroxy acids are alike, $K_{Ni.Histidine.L} - K_{Ni.L}$ is of the order of 0.8 to 1.0 irrespective of whether L = hydroxy or the mercapto acid. This shows that in both cases the factor responsible for the lowering of the values of $K_{M.Histidine.L}$ is electrostatic repulsion. In case of $K_{Ni.NTA.L}$ (L = mercapto acid) also $K_{Ni.NTA.L} - K_{Ni.L}$ is of the same order as in the cases of systems where L is a σ bonding ligand⁴. However, greater stability of M-S bond in binary complexes has been attributed to M-S π interaction¹⁵⁻¹⁷. M-S π bonding, if present, should have been favoured more in MAL than in ML⁵, thus the difference $K_{ML} - K_{MAL}$ should be less if L is a π bonding ligand. Since the difference is of the same order in case of hydroxy and mercapto acid complexes, it can be argued that M-S π bonding is not significant. The greater stability of M-S bond is due to the strengthening of M-S σ bond^{18,19}.

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